

GCAQE Meeting Introduction

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ABBREVIATIONS

CAA Civil Aviation Authority

Welcome everybody.

We are going to have a very good two days—of that I am certain. To start with, today is my birthday. On the basis that it is never too late to learn, I intend to continue with my education; an invitation I extend to so many of the experts upon whom we have to rely to make such important decisions on our behalf.

Firstly, I want to congratulate EasyJet for their momentous decision to test the Pall Aerospace filtration system in their aircraft. I have no doubts that the system will benefit pilots, crew, and passengers, and, of course in the long term, the EasyJet bank balance. I have no doubt the outcome will be successful.

The Sunday Times carried an accompanying announcement by the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) of a “care pathway” for victims of fume events at a specialist clinic at St Thomas’ Hospital, London, however, this filled me with skepticism. St Thomas’ have form on organophosphate poisoning which doesn’t cover them with glory, but that debate is for another day.

Over the last weeks and months I have been doing a lot of thinking around this conundrum. This has been helped greatly by my meeting with an American bioethicist, Diane O’Leary. One of the advantages of working in a job like mine is that you meet all sorts of wonderfully sharp-minded people. Several of you are in our midst today.

Diane has pointed me in a completely different direction to that assumed by the establishment to be the only one upon which they will act upon our submissions. I think that we will all have to acknowledge that it will be extremely difficult to obtain enough scientific evidence to prove conclusively that the ill health being experienced by some pilots, crew and passengers is the result of exposure to chemically contaminated air in aircraft. It cannot be for want of trying. For the 11 years that I have been patron of GCAQE I have asked hundreds of parliamentary questions for written answer; I have asked oral questions and, with Susan Michaelis and Tristan Loraine, I’ve had meetings with Ministers and members of the CAA. I’ve also written letters to all and sundry. Obfuscation has been the continued objective of officials from the CAA, the Department for Transport, the Health and Safety Executive, the Department of Health and Ministers from those departments.

The recent response from Dr Simon Clarke, Head of the Transport Sector of the Health and Safety Executive, to an invitation to Martin Temple to attend this meeting, is a prime example of the mind-set of the officials. He says: “*We can see nothing in this most recent or previous evidence that provides clear and consistent evidence of causal long-term health effects on air crew related to cabin air quality in line with standard epidemiological and toxicological assessment.*” Clearly, they belong to the ‘closed minds brigade’.

There was a research study conducted by Cranfield University where, perversely, in over 100 test flights, there was not one fume event recorded. Based on the published results of this research, the nearest we have got to any admission is the statement from the Committee on Toxicity of Chemicals in Food and the Environment, also known as the COT, in their

position paper published in 2013. Here they admit that “...uncertainties remain, and a toxic mechanism for symptoms cannot confidently be ruled out.” They suggest that the cost/benefit of further research must be calculated before further research, which they acknowledge is a factor, is commissioned.

Now we get to the kernel of the problem. It strikes me that, no matter how much scientific evidence you provide as to causation, it will never be enough because to admit that there is a problem is also to admit legal and financial liability. We know that the airline operators have a legal responsibility to provide a safe working environment for their employees. We also know that if they can be shown to have failed in their duty there are likely to be claims for compensation.

There is a familiar saying – ‘If you find yourself in a hole, stop digging’. I am suggesting that it is time the manufacturers, the airline operators, the CAA and government to follow EasyJet and stop digging and I will explain why.

The question is this: do the authorities and the airline manufacturers and operators have an ethical duty to act now, given the current state of the difference of opinion about the presence of a problem, or is it all right to continue with the status quo? What does the current state of uncertainty indicate in terms of the right course of action?

One subject upon which we can all agree is the finances. If we acknowledge that the airlines have a great deal of power when it comes to influencing policy decisions of this kind, then we should be able to agree that, if there is a health threat caused by unfiltered cabin air, then concerns about that threat should outweigh concerns about addressing the problem on the basis of scientific evidence. After all, as we have heard in the past, and I know that we will hear again in the next two days, there are relatively inexpensive filters which will do the job.

I believe that there is an obligation to err on the side of caution. We should start by listing all those likely to be

affected: pilots and crew, passengers and ground staff. We should then list the potential harms and benefits to each from delaying action rather than acting promptly. We know that there are both short- and long-term risks of moderate to severe health problems for pilots and crew and that there is a likely short term risk of mild to moderate health problems to passengers. There is also some risk of very serious harm to passengers and crew as a result of poor decision making based on the neurological compromise of the pilots.

Do these risks outweigh the benefits of continuing to research the problem – a process which is necessarily slow because of a lack of funding, before we take action? The only benefits appear to be cost-related; that is costs related to public health efforts, to research and the costs to the airlines. There is a great benefit to caution. If, as the airline operators, the CAA and government claim, there is no problem with cabin air at all, then researching the problem slowly allows us to get a very clear picture of the details before acting in a way that is rash and unsupported.

I will give you an example. We have one flight, pilots, crew and a set of passengers. As the flight is about to take off, we discover that there is an unclear level of risk of air contamination. It might be contaminated to the extent that would compromise the pilot’s decision making. It might pose a short-term health risk for passengers and crew. Perhaps continued exposure would pose long term health risks to the pilot and crew. It might pose a lifelong risk to an unborn fetus. Would it be ethical to let that flight take off without immediately looking into the problem?

It seems not. If we become aware of this kind of potential threat at exactly this level of certainty for any particular flight before take-off, I am sure that we would all recognize that the flight should not be allowed to take off until we can make sure the air is safe to breathe. When the problem applies to a particular group of human beings we can see readily the need to respond to uncertainty in a protective way.

It looks simple to me. The benefits of acting now, for the sake of caution, far outweigh the benefits of acting slowly. What is the ethical response to uncertainty in this case? Is it acceptable to respond to uncertainty by allowing the risk to persist, or is there an ethical obligation to respond to uncertainty in a protective way that errs on the side of caution? Sometimes it is hard to see the answer to the question at the level of patient groups and policy when it is generally easy to see at the level of individuals. It is then that we can assume that the same obligations hold at the level of policy.

Perhaps we are blinding ourselves with the obsession for science.